

Investigation on Structural, Dielectric, Ferroelectric, and Piezoelectric properties of (1-x)PbTiO₃ – (x)Bi(Zn_{2/3}Nb_{1/3})O₃ solid solutions

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Abstract

Single phase (1-x) PbTiO₃ – (x)Bi(Zn_{2/3}Nb_{1/3})O₃ (x=0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) binary piezoceramics were prepared using solid-state reaction technique. Rietveld analysis confirms the tetragonal phase with *P4mm* space group for all the compositions studied. The lattice parameters and unit cell volume are shown to increase with increasing Bi(Zn_{2/3}Nb_{1/3})O₃ (BZN) substitution in PbTiO₃(PT). The microstructure of the samples exhibits average grain size distribution (< 10 μm). Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) and X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) analysis confirmed the chemical composition of the prepared samples. Temperature and frequency-dependent dielectric studies revealed normal ferroelectric behavior in (1-x)PT-(x)BZN. High remnant polarization and saturation polarization were attained for 0.74PT-0.26 BZN samples. The Curie temperature (T_c), dielectric constant (ε_r), and remnant polarization decrease with increasing BZN substitution. The recoverable energy-storage density (J_{reco}) of 0.2105 J/cm³ and efficiency (η) of 67 % were achieved for 0.74PT-0.26BZN and 0.68PT-0.32BZN ceramics, respectively. The enhanced piezoelectric coefficient charge d₃₃ ~ 409 pC/N was observed for 0.74PT – 0.26BZN. This study provides the route for exploring new piezoelectric materials with enhanced electrical properties.

Keywords

Solid-state sintering, Dielectric properties, Ferroelectrics, Piezoelectric, XRF

1. Introduction

The last five decades have evidence of a large interest in piezoceramics like PbTiO_3 (PT), $\text{Pb}[\text{Zr}(x)\text{Ti}(1-x)]\text{O}_3$ (PZT), $\text{Pb}(\text{Zn}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3$ -PT (PZN-PT), $\text{Pb}(\text{Mn}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3$ -PT (PMN-PT), and $\text{Pb}(\text{Sc}_{1/2}\text{Nb}_{1/2})\text{O}_3$ -PT (PSN-PT) due to their ultrahigh properties. Piezoelectric materials have attracted significant interest in sensors, transducers, actuators, non-destructive evaluations, microelectro-mechanical systems, medical diagnostics, and piezocatalysis [1-15]. PZT, PMN-PT, and PZN-PT are the most widely exploited and extensively used piezoelectric materials, having secured a permanent place in the piezoelectric industries. However, the high toxicity of lead oxide is further enhanced due to its volatilization at high temperature particularly during calcination, sintering, and single crystal growth causing environmental pollution. Therefore, it is a valuable task to develop lead-free/low-lead-based PT piezoceramics with enhanced piezoelectric properties [1-7].

BaTiO_3 (BT), $\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3$ (NBT), and $\text{K}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{NbO}_3$ (KNN)-based materials have received great attention and have been expected to replace Pb-based materials [16-18]. The Bibased materials exhibit high electrical polarization from their lone-pair electron, and moderate piezoelectric properties. However, the above-mentioned lead-free materials have low Curie temperature (TC) (<300 oC), difficult to prepare stoichiometric compounds due to Na, K, and Bi elements that are highly volatile in nature, which results in difficulty in the poling process due to high leakage current. Also, these Pb-free systems have a moderate piezoelectric response, which limits practical device applications in harsh environments [16-21].

Additionally, the morphotropic phase boundary (MPB) of KNN-based materials' nonvertical behavior, introduces significant temperature sensitivity to piezoelectric behavior. This characteristic is highly undesirable from a device perspective, emphasizing the need for solutions that address these temperature-related challenges for enhanced device stability [16-21]. It is worth searching for alternative

piezoelectric materials with low lead content with superior Tc, dielectric, ferro, piezo, and electro-mechanical properties. Thus, the ferroelectric PT-Bi (A, B)O₃ (A = Ni, Mg, Zn, Sn, and B = Ti, Zr, W, Hf, Nb) solid solutions exhibit a high Curie temperature (TC) and easily tailor to achieve excellent piezoelectric properties [22-29]. Further, the Pb-based end members like PT, PbFeO₃, PMN, PZN, etc., form a pure perovskite structure under an ambient atmosphere. However, another end member Bi(A, B)O₃ requires high pressure (~ 5 GPa) to form a pure perovskite phase [16-21]. As a result, Bi(A, B)O₃ materials are frequently made from PT i.e., PT-Bi(Mg_{1/2}Ti_{1/2})O₃ [22], PT-Bi(Zn_{1/2}Zr_{1/2})O₃ [23], PT-Bi(Mg_{1/2}Zr_{1/2})O₃ [22, 23], PT-Bi(Ni_{1/2}Ti_{1/2})O₃ [24], PT-Bi(Zn_{1/2}Ti_{1/2})O₃ [25], PT-Bi(Zn_{1/2}Sn_{1/2})O₃ [25], PT-Bi(Mg_{3/4}W_{1/4})O₃ [26], PT-Bi(Zn_{3/4}W_{1/4})O₃ [27], PT-Bi(Ni_{2/3}Nb_{1/3})O₃ [28], etc. Grinberg et.al. have explained by theoretical calculation, that the enhanced ferroelectric and piezoelectric properties of PT-Bi (A, B)O₃ solid solutions are due to the interplay between the non-centrosymmetric displacement of A-site ions [23]. Further, structural distortion and polarization were also determined in PT-Bi (A, B)O₃ solid solutions from the first principles calculations [23].

Among the family of PT-Bi (A, B)O₃ solid solutions, the solid solutions of PT-Bi (Ni_{1/2}Hf_{1/2})O₃ [30] and PT-BiScO₃ [31, 32] displayed the highest d_{33} value ($d_{33} \sim 450$ pC/N). However, Hf and Sc are high cost, which leads to unfavorable for commercial application and mass production. Recently, Rong et.al. observed the high d_{33} (~ 425 pC/N) value in cost-effective and low Pb-content solid solutions such as (1-x) PT-(x) Bi (Zn_{2/3}Nb_{1/3})O₃ (PT-xBZN) and (1-x) PT-(x) Bi(Ni_{1/2}Zr_{1/2})O₃ (PT-xBNZ) [33]. The Bi-ion has a smaller atomic radius than Pb, and induces an increment in the displacement of A-site ions, which enhances spontaneous polarization (PS) owing to the variation in A-O bond length. The displacement of the Bi-ion results in the formation of four short-range Bi-O bonds, while the remaining O-ions make a minor contribution to the Bi-O bond, which makes a Bi-O₄ complex within the Bi-O₁₂ cuboctahedral structure. The PT-xBZN and PT-xBNZ solid solutions are suitable for high-temperature piezoelectric device applications [24, 33, 34-37]. In recent studies on (1-x) PT - (x) BZN ceramics and single crystals, the composition range was restricted from x = 0.00 to 0.30.

(1-x) PT-(x) BZN (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) solid solutions on structural, microstructural, dielectric, ferroelectric, energy storage, and piezoelectric properties have not been reported. The present investigation attempts to study the phase formation, microstructure, dielectric, energy storage, electromechanical and piezoelectric properties on (1-x) PT-(x) BZN (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) ceramics. Subsequently, this research could lead to an effective method to fabricate hightemperature piezoelectric materials.

2. Experimental procedure

(1-x) PT-(x) BZN (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) solid solutions were prepared via solid-state reaction method. High-purity Bi₂O₃, PbO, TiO₂, ZnO, and Nb₂O₅ (Alfa Aesar, purity 99.99%) were used for the synthesis of polycrystalline materials. Stoichiometric amounts of these materials were accurately weighed and mixed in an agate mortar. 2 mol% of excess PbO and Bi₂O₃ were added in stoichiometric materials to minimize the volatilization of PbO and Bi₂O₃ during high-temperature sintering. The starting precursors were homogeneously mixed in a planetary ball mill with ZrO₂ balls using acetone as the solvent for 10-12 hours. The ball-milled powders were calcined in a MoSi₂ furnace at 850°C for 6 hours. The calcined powders were pressed to form green compact disc-shaped pellets (10 mm dia, 1 mm thickness) using 4 wt % polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) solution. Ceramic pellets were placed in a platinum (Pt) crucible and sintered in the temperature range 1050°C - 1150°C for 2 hours. Pressed pellets were buried in polycrystalline powder to minimize the Pb and Bi evaporation during the sintering process.

The density of the prepared pellets was measured using the Archimedes method. The room temperature crystal structure and phase purity of the synthesized samples were characterized using PAN analytical high-resolution X-ray powder Diffraction (XRPD) using the CuK α ($\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$) source. For the XRPD measurements, the powders were obtained from the crushing of the sintered pellets and annealed at 650°C for 6 h to remove the strain formed during the crushing. Rietveld refinements were done using the FullProf package [38, 39] to identify the crystal structure and its lattice parameter. The microstructure of

the sintered ceramics was analyzed by Field-Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM) (Zeiss). The chemical compositions of the sintered ceramics were checked by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) (Zeiss) and x-ray fluorescence (XRF) (Rigaku). Silver electrodes were fabricated on both sides of the sintered pellets of (1-x) PT-(x) BZN (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32). The dielectric constant and dielectric loss were examined in the temperature range of 50 to 500°C at various frequencies (250 – 7500 Hz) using a Wayne Kerr LCR meter. The polarization–electric field (P-E) loops were evaluated by precision Premier II tester (Radiant technology). From the P-E loops, the energy storage density (W_{rec}), energy loss density (W_{loss}), and efficiency of energy storage density (η) were calculated. The samples were poled by direct current (DC) contact poling in silicone oil. The piezoelectric coefficient d_{33} was measured using a Piezo tester (Piezometer PM 300, UK).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Phase Purity and Structural Investigation

The phase purity of the sintered (x) PT-(1-x) BZN (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) solid solutions were confirmed by XRPD measurements as shown in Fig. 1a. All prepared samples exhibit single phase perovskite structure without any pyrochlore phase. All the peak profiles in the diffraction pattern could be indexed with tetragonal $P4mm$ space group [22, 31, 35-37]. The ionic radii of Zn^{2+} , Nb^{5+} and Ti^{4+} are 0.74 Å, 0.64 Å, and 0.605 Å, respectively. Zn^{2+} and Nb^{5+} are more favourable to occupy Ti^{4+} -site of (1-x) PT-(x) BZN ceramics [22, 31, 39] due to the Zn^{2+} and Nb^{5+} ions have smaller ionic radii than Ti^{4+} . Bi^{3+} is more favorable to occupy Pb^{2+} in the A-site of PT-BZN ceramics due to Bi^{3+} ion having smaller ionic radii than Pb^{2+} . It was confirmed by peaks shifting (see Fig. 1b) towards the lower angle side due to lattice expansion. The powder XRPD patterns clearly describe that BZN is diffused into the parent PT solid matrix. To estimate the lattice strain of (x)PT-(1-x) BZN (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) solid solutions, the first seven peaks of the diffraction profile are analyzed using the Williamson-Hall (W-H) equation

$$\beta_{hkl} \cos\theta = \frac{k\lambda}{D} + 4\epsilon \sin\theta \quad (1)$$

Where β , λ , K , θ , D , and ε are full-width half maxima, wavelength of X-Ray source, shape factor of the peak, angle of Bragg's diffraction, crystalline size and lattice strain, respectively. The lattice strain (ε) was calculated from the slope of the linear fitting. The W-H plots of the (1-x) PT-(x) BZN ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, \text{ and } 0.32$) composition were shown in Fig. 2(a-d). The calculated values of ε are presented in Table 1. The positive value of ε implies that the lattice has undergone expansion. This usually happens when an ion with higher ionic radii replaces an ion with smaller ionic radii. The result is in excellent agreement with the increase in unit cell volume observed from the Rietveld analysis of the prepared (1-x) PT-(x) BZN ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, \text{ and } 0.32$) solid solutions.

We have also performed the quantitative analysis of the XRPD patterns of (1-x) PT-(x) BZN ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, \text{ and } 0.32$) solid solutions using the Rietveld refinement technique. In the refinement, the peak shape and width were modeled using the pseudo-Voigt function while the background can be described by linear interpolation method. All parameters (scale factor, zero error, background points, width parameters (u, v, w), lattice parameters (a, b, c), thermal parameters, and positional coordinates) were varied during the refinement except the occupancy which was fixed to the nominal composition. Fig. 3(a-d) displays the observed (filled red circle) and calculated (black continuous line) XRPD profiles for (1-x) PT-(x) BZN ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, \text{ and } 0.32$) solid solutions using the tetragonal structure in the $P4mm$ space group. The observed and calculated profiles show a satisfactory fit for all compositions (x), as can be seen from the flat difference profile given as the bottom (blue continuous) line in the same figure. We do not observe any structural phase transition as a result of BZN substitution in PT, i.e. the crystal structure remains tetragonal in the $P4mm$ space group for all the compositions. The structural parameters obtained after the Rietveld analysis of (1-x) PT-(x) BZN ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, \text{ and } 0.32$) solid solutions are presented in Table 1. The calculated unit cell parameters are consistent with the previous reports [31, 35, 36].

The composition dependence of the lattice parameters of (1-x) PT-(x) BZN ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, \text{ and } 0.32$) solid solutions is shown in Fig. 3(e). The unit cell parameter increases linearly with increasing the BZN composition. This increasing trend of unit cell parameters can be attributed to the fact that the

ionic radius of Zn^{2+} (0.74 Å), and Nb^{5+} (0.64 Å), is larger than that of Ti^{4+} (0.605 Å) and hence substitution of BZN at the PT-site would lead to lattice expansion. Thus, XRPD confirms the single-phase formation of (1-x) PT-(x) BZN (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) solid solutions.

3.2 Microstructural and Compositional analysis

The microstructure of sintered ceramics was examined to study the impact of BZN on their microstructure. Fig. 4(a-d) shows FE-SEM images of the (1-x) PT-(x) BZN (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) sintered samples. All samples exhibit dense microstructures and well-developed grains without visible porosity. The grain size distribution is analyzed quantitatively using the linear intercept method by Image J software. The calculated average grain sizes of (1-x) PT-(x) BZN (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) sintered samples are ~ 9.8, 7.86, 7.11, and 6.07 μm, respectively. In this work, BZN can form cation vacancies, which accumulate at the grain boundary and suppress the mobility of grain boundaries due to the pinning effect. The average grain size variation in the (1-x) PT-(x) BZN (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) ceramics can be attributed to the formation of cation vacancies by BZN substitution. From Fig. 5(a-d), the substitution of BZN decreased the grain size, which indicates that BZN inhibited grain growth in PT-BZN ceramics. The relative density of all sintered PT-BZN samples exceeded 90% of the theoretical values. The chemical composition of the prepared (1-x) PT-(x) BZN (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) was recorded by EDS and XRF analysis. The results are given in Table 2. Oxygen was excluded from this analysis as EDS is not sensitive to lighter atoms. It is evident from the table that the chemical composition of the prepared samples are close to the nominal composition.

3.3. Dielectric Properties

Figure 6 shows the dielectric constant and loss of (a) 0.74PT – 0.26BZN, (b) 0.72PT – 0.28BZN, (c) 0.70PT – 0.30BZN, and (d) 0.68PT – 0.32BZN in the temperature range 350 to 500°C for various frequencies (250 Hz, 500 Hz, 1000 Hz, 2500 Hz, 5000 Hz, and 7500 Hz). It is evident from 6 (a) that 0.74PT – 0.26BZN composition shows a dielectric peak at 467°C which is in excellent agreement with the

previous reports [22, 31, 35-37]. The sharp dielectric peak indicates a first-order phase transition. The dielectric peak is believed to arise due to the phase transition from ferroelectric to para-electric phase (TC). The TC is observed at 462°C (0.72PT – 0.28BZN), 450°C (0.70PT – 0.30BZN), and 444°C (0.68PT – 0.32BZN), which can be seen clearly in Fig 6(b-d). The dielectric maxima exhibit a clear independence on frequency. The results indicate the presence of macro-sized ferroelectric regions, which are analogous to normal ferroelectrics. The dielectric loss ($\tan \delta$) is increased with an increase in the BZN substitution, which is mostly due to the increased conductivity. As shown in Figs. 6 (e), the dielectric properties of (1-x)PT-xBZN samples decrease with increase in BZN substitution, because the substitution of Zn^{2+} and Nb^{5+} ions replaced Ti^{4+} ions. The occupation of Zn^{2+} and Nb^{5+} ions on the B-site promotes the structural disorder. The 0.70PT – 0.30BZN and 0.68PT – 0.32BZN samples reveal low dielectric constant. This result is consistent with the previous reports [35-37]. Thus, the dielectric constant variation is strongly structural disorder dependent on the samples. Figure 6 (f) shows the TC as a function of the BZN substitution of studied PT-based solid solutions. A higher TC usually indicates a stronger polar state and a more stable ferroelectric phase [35, 37]. The decrease in TC in the (1-x)PT-xBZN solid solution with the increased substitution of BZN for PT may be attributed to the decrease in the tetragonality of the structure. These results show that (1-x)PT-xBZN may be promising, high-temperature piezoelectric applications. Table 3 displays the comparison of dielectric, ferroelectric, energy storage, and piezoelectric properties of (1-x) PT-(x) BZN (x = 0.26,

0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) with reported PT materials.

To understand the dielectric peak more clearly, we use the 1 kHz dielectric constant data of all compositions using the Curie-Weiss (CW) law $\epsilon = C/(T-TCW)$ [40-44], where C and TCW are the CW constant and CW temperature, respectively. The CW constants C' and C represent the slope of the linear fit below and above TC as temperature changes [45, 46]. From Fig. 7(a-d), the C values of 0.74PT – 0.26BZN, 0.72PT – 0.28BZN, 0.70PT – 0.30BZN, and 0.68PT – 0.32BZN are 2.98×10^{-7} , 8.12×10^{-8} , 4.88×10^{-8} , and 7.37×10^{-8} respectively. The observed magnitude is $\sim 10^{-8}$, showing that all the prepared ceramics

were ferroelectric materials [40]. Typically, a C/C' value below 4 indicates a second-order ferroelectric phase transition (relaxor ferroelectric), while a value above 4 indicates a first-order ferroelectric phase transition (normal ferroelectric) [45, 46]. The calculated C/C' ratios for the (1-x)PT-(x)BZN samples were found to be greater than 4. Dielectric measurements indicate that first-order normal ferroelectric phase transitions occur for the (1-x)PT - (x)BZN samples.

Diffuse dielectric phenomena can be found for (1-x)PT - (x)BZN samples that are described by the modified Curie–Weiss law as follows [47]

$$\ln(1/\varepsilon - 1/\varepsilon_{\max}) = \gamma \ln(T - T_m) + C \quad (2)$$

Where the ε is the dielectric constant and its maximum value is ε_{\max} . Fig 8(a - d) show the Vogelfulcher plot between $\ln(1/\varepsilon - 1/\varepsilon_{\max})$ vs $\ln(T - T_m)$ for the (1-x)PT-(x)BZN ceramics. The γ values were calculated from the above-mentioned modified CW equation. The γ values are 0.89 (0.74PT – 0.26BZN), 0.87 (0.72PT – 0.28BZN), 0.68(0.70PT – 0.30BZN), and 0.69 (0.68PT – 0.32BZN), respectively. The observed γ values are less than 1, which indicates a normal ferroelectrics state [45, 46].

3.4 Ferroelectric and Energy-storage properties

Ferroelectric properties of (1-x)PT-(x)BZN ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30,$ and 0.32) ceramics are depicted in Fig. 9 Polarization vs Electric field hysteresis loop at 10 Hz. The saturated and slightly asymmetric P–E loops were observed for all (1-x)PT-(x)BZN ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30,$ and 0.32) samples. The gap in P-E loops confirms conductivity due to the existence of defects. The enhanced ferroelectric properties such as remnant polarization ($P_r \sim 26.7 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$), maximum polarization ($P_s \sim 40 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$) and coercive field ($E_c \sim 15.9 \text{ kV}/\text{cm}$) were obtained for 0.74PT – 0.26BZN ceramics. The defect concentration and ionic polarizability can influence polarization value. All the prepared samples exhibited typical ferroelectric P-E loops, which indicate a strong ferroelectric state. The decrease in P_r and P_s with increased BZN substitution is because of the substitution of Zn^{2+} and Nb^{5+} ions in Ti^{4+} ions.

The internal bias field E_i is calculated by the formula $E_i = E_{c+} + E_{c-} / 2$, where E_{c+} and E_{c-} are the positive and negative coercive fields, respectively. Internal bias E_i decreases from 0.075 to 0.05 kV/cm with increased BZN substitution. The internal bias is closely related to the sintering, poling, acceptor–oxygen vacancy defect dipoles, dopants, grain boundary, and aging time, which will affect the internal bias field. The internal bias is an important parameter in evaluating dielectric loss and mechanical loss. Therefore, ferroelectric materials with higher internal bias are desirable for high-power electromechanical applications, because the internal bias is proportionally related to the mechanical quality factor.

The energy storage properties can be estimated from the P–E curve by using the integral equations [48, 49],

$$J_{reco} = \int_{P_r}^{P_{Max}} E dp \quad (3)$$

$$J_{loss} = \int_0^{P_{Max}} E dp \quad (4)$$

$$\eta = \frac{W_{rec}}{W_{loss} + W_{rec}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

J_{reco} and J_{loss} can also be determined from P-E loop values, 0.2105, 0.2027, 0.1947, 0.1898 J/cm³ and 0.1697, 0.1458, 0.1517, 0.1217 J/cm³ for 0.74PT – 0.26BZN, 0.72PT – 0.28BZN, 0.70PT – 0.30BZN, and 0.68PT – 0.32BZN ceramics at room temperature, respectively. High energy density, low energy loss density (J_{loss}), and energy storage efficiency (η) are very important for device applications [50-55]. The calculated corresponding energy-storage efficiency η values of 61%, 59%, 62 % and 67 % for 0.74PT – 0.26BZN, 0.72PT – 0.28BZN, 0.70PT – 0.30BZN, and 0.68PT – 0.32BZN, respectively. The energy-storage (J_{reco}) properties of (1-x)PT-(x)BZN ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, \text{ and } 0.32$) ceramics are comparable with previously published Pb-based materials displayed in Table 3. The 0.68PT – 0.32BZN ceramic exhibits a lower energy storage efficiency ($\eta \sim 67 \%$) than other reported Pb based materials such as PMN-PT, PbZrO₃–SrTiO₃, 2 mol% Pr³⁺:0.24PIN-0.42PMN-0.34PT and (Pb 1-x Lax)(Zr0.70Ti0.30) 1-x/4 O3 ($x = 0.090$), respectively

[37, 53-55]. Therefore, (1-x)PT-(x)BZN ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30,$ and 0.32) ceramics is not well suited to electrical energy storage applications.

3.4. Piezoelectric properties

The piezoelectric charge coefficient d_{33} of (1-x)PT-x BZN solid solutions ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30,$ and 0.32) of poled ceramic samples are shown in Fig 10. The highest values of piezoelectric coefficient (d_{33}) ~ 409 pC/N has been obtained for the composition 0.74PT – 0.26BZN. Further, with increasing the BZN content in PT the d_{33} values decrease [56-58]. The piezoelectric properties in (1-x)PT-xBZN are affected by several reasons described as follows: (1) Conductivity in the samples is proportional to the concentration of Zn and Nb ions, and also the associated oxygen vacancies, Pb and Bi loss during sintering decreases d_{33} ; (2) BZN substitution can reduce the grain size of the sintered pellets and its distribution can also potentially affect the piezoelectricity.

4. Conclusions

The solid-state reaction route was used to synthesize (1-x) PbTiO₃-(x) Bi (Zn_{2/3}Nb_{1/3})O₃ ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30,$ and 0.32) solid solutions. Powder X-ray analysis confirms the tetragonal structure within the $P4mm$ space group without any pyrochlore phases. The substitution of BZN inhibits grain growth in (1-x)PT-x BZN ferroelectric systems. The optimized dielectric and ferroelectric properties of 0.74PT – 0.26BZN ceramics possess maximum values of $\epsilon_m \sim 20500$, $T_c \sim 467^\circ\text{C}$, $P_r \sim 26.7 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$, and $d_{33} \sim 410$ pC/N. The recoverable energy-storage density (J_{reco}) of $0.2105 \text{ J}/\text{cm}^3$ and efficiency (η) of 67 % were achieved for 0.74PT-0.26BZN and 0.68PT- 0.32BZN ceramics, respectively. The piezoelectric properties of the (1-x)PT-x BZN solid solutions ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30,$ and 0.32) can be further enhanced with optimized sintering, microstructure, defect concentration, and domain engineering.

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Author contributions

P. Aravinth Kumar: Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – Original Draft. **G. Gopi:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation. **G.Anandha Babu:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision.

Data availability

The data presented in this study are available within the article.

Declarations

Conflict of interest The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Figure 1(a). The XRPD patterns of $(1-x)\text{PT}-(x)\text{BZN}$ ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, \text{ and } 0.32$) ceramics **(b)** Illustrate the shifting of the peaks (100) and (111) in diffraction profile.

Figure 2. Williamson-Hall Plots of (a) 0.74PT-0.26BZN, (b) 0.72PT-0.28BZN, (c) 0.70PT-0.30BZN, and (d) 0.68PT-0.32BZN ceramics

Figure 3. Rietveld refinement fit of $(1-x)\text{PT}-(x)\text{BZN}$, $x =$ **(a)** 0.26, **(b)** 0.28, **(c)** 0.30, and **(d)** 0.32 ceramics and **(e)** lattice parameters 'a' and 'c' of $(1-x)\text{PT}-(x)\text{BZN}$ ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30,$ and 0.32) ceramics.

Figure 4. FE-SEM images of the (1-x)PT-(x)BZN ceramics with x ratios of **(a)** 0.26, **(b)** 0.28, **(c)** 0.30, and **(d)** 0.32.

Figure 5. Histogram of the grain size of (1-x)PT-(x)BZN ceramics with x ratios of **(a)** 0.26, **(b)** 0.28, **(c)** 0.30, and **(d)** 0.32.

Figure 6. Piezoelectric coefficient d_{33} of (1-x)PT-(x)BZN ($x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30,$ and 0.32) ceramic.

Figure 7. Variation of the dielectric constant and loss parts of $(1-x)\text{PT}-(x)\text{BZN}$ ceramics at various frequencies (a) 0.26, (b) 0.28, (c) 0.30, and (d) 0.32. (e) $(1-x)\text{PT}-(x)\text{BZN}$ in magnified view of dielectric constant near T_c for 250 Hz and change of T_c with BZN substitution illustrate in (f).

Figure 8. Curie-Weiss fitting of dielectric constant of (1-x)PT-(x)BZN ceramics measured at 1 KHz for $x =$ (a) 0.26, (b) 0.28, (c) 0.30, and (d) 0.32 (Open circle: observed data and Red line: linear fitting).

Figure 9. Variation of $\ln(1/\epsilon - 1/\epsilon_{\max})$ as a function of $\ln(T - T_c)$ for the $(1-x)\text{PT}-(x)\text{BZN}$ ceramics measured at 1 KHz for $x =$ (a) 0.26, (b) 0.28, (c) 0.30, and (d) 0.32.

Figure 10. P-E loops of (1-x)PT-(x)BZN ceramics under various field strength 60 kV.

Table 1. Structural parameter obtained from Rietveld refinement density and lattice strain obtained from WH plot for (1-x)PT-(x)BZN (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) ceramics

Composition	x = 0.26	x = 0.28	x = 0.30	x = 0.32
Lattice Parameter				
a = b (Å)	3.902(5)	3.9099(2)	3.9147(9)	3.9172(4)
c (Å)	4.2054(3)	4.2143(4)	4.2264(6)	4.2319(2)
Unit-cell Volume				
V (Å ³)	64.0297(15)	64.4253(28)	64.7690(12)	64.9347(22)
Lattice strain $\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$	3.12	3.34	3.37	3.49
Crystalline Size (nm)	157.16	158.31	158.95	159.45
Density	89 %	91 %	94 %	90 %
Fitting Parameters				
χ^2	2.58	2.04	3.29	2.89
R _{wp}	6.58	7.78	8.15	8.65

Table 2. Results of EDX and XRF analysis of (x) PT-(1-x) BZN (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) ceramics.

Elements	74:26 Weight %			72:28 Weight %			70:30 Weight %			68:32 Weight %		
	Expected	Observed		Expected	Observed		Expected	Observed		Expected	Observed	
		EDX	XRF									
Pb	58.4	57.7	58.2	56.7	56.3	56.5	55	54.6	54.8	53.3	53	53.2
Ti	13.5	13.3	13.3	13.2	12.7	12.9	12.7	12.3	12.5	12.3	12.9	12.5
Bi	20.7	19.9	20.3	22.2	21.6	21.9	23.8	23.5	23.7	25.3	24.9	24.9
Zn	4.3	4.8	4.4	4.6	5.5	5.1	4.9	5.3	4.9	5.3	4.9	5.2
Nb	3.1	4.3	3.8	3.3	3.9	3.6	3.6	3.4	3.6	3.8	4.3	4.2

Table 3. Comparison of the Dielectric, Ferroelectric, Piezoelectric and energy storage properties of (1-x)PT-(x)BZN (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32) and similar materials

Composition	T _C (°C)	E _C (kV/cm)	P _r (μV/cm ²)	d ₃₃	η	J _{loss}	Ref
(1-x)PbTiO ₃ - (x)Bi(Zn _{1/3} Nb _{2/3})O ₃ (x = 0.26, 0.28, 0.30, and 0.32)	470- 440	16-17	21-19	400- 320	59-67	0.1217 – 0.1697	Present work
(1-x)PbTiO ₃ - (x)Ba(Zr _{1/2} Ni _{1/2})O ₃ (x = 0.38, 0.40, 0.42, and 0.48)	280- 320	17-24	25-31	260- 390			30
(0.49)PbTiO ₃ - (0.51)Ba(Nb _{1/2} Ni _{1/2})O ₃	365	37	39	265			26
(1-x)PbTiO ₃ - (x)Bi(Mg _{1/2} Ni _{1/2})O ₃ (x = 0.60, 0.63 and 0.65)	420- 470	38	55	210- 240			27
(0.55)PbTiO ₃ - (0.45)Bi(Mg _{1/2} Zr _{1/2})O ₃	190	25	17	140			22
(1-x)PbTiO ₃ - (x)Bi(Zn _{1/2} Ti _{1/2})O ₃ (x = 0.60, 0.70, 0.80, 0.90 and 1.00)	520- 700						23
(1-x)PbTiO ₃ - (x)Bi(Zn _{3/4} W _{1/4})O ₃ (x = 0.60, 0.70 and 0.80)	220- 270	6	17	100- 140			31

